

A STUDY OF LIFE INSURANCE BUSINESS: PRE & POST LIBERALIZED ERA

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ABSTRACT

The insurance industry of India consists of 57 insurance companies of which 24 are in life insurance business and 33 are non-life insurers. Among the life insurers, Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) is the sole public sector company. Apart from that, among the non-life insurers there are six public sector insurers. In addition to these, there is sole national re-insurer, namely, General Insurance Corporation of India (GIC Re). Other stakeholders in Indian Insurance market include agents (individual and corporate), brokers, surveyors and third party administrators servicing health insurance claims.

Out of 33 non-life insurance companies, five private sector insurers are registered to underwrite policies exclusively in health, personal accident and travel insurance segments. They are Star Health and Allied Insurance Company Ltd, Apollo Munich Health Insurance Company Ltd, Max Bupa Health Insurance Company Ltd, Religare Health Insurance Company Ltd and Cigna TTK Health Insurance Company Ltd. There are two more specialised insurers belonging to public sector, namely, Export Credit Guarantee Corporation of India for Credit Insurance and Agriculture Insurance Company Ltd for crop insurance.

Key-Words: GIC, LIC, IRDA, KYC.

INTRODUCTION

According to India's Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA), in April-May 2018, premium from new life insurance business increased 7.33 percent year-on-year to Rs 201.18 billion (US\$ 3.12 billion). Surfing smooth at the crest of the digital transformation wave Indian Insurance sector is showing tremendous progress in addressing the demands of customers.

The Current Scenario:

GOIs flagship initiative Digital India has an incredible impact in shaping Indian industries for a better tomorrow. Electronic know-your-customer (e-KYC), approval of 15 Foreign Direct Investment and allowing 35% stake to e-commerce being the primary game-changing enablers.

Transformation to digital has been a key priority and focus for insurers. Be it implementing GST, transformation to digital or changes in regulations, a series of changes in the Indian Insurance sector have made it more customer-centric and transparent.

Insurers today are rightly focused on embracing digital strategies, tools, and technology to deliver bespoke customer experience over all channels. Technologies like AI, IOT, chatbots, ML etc are already helping companies to understand their customer better and make the buying

process seamless. As we move ahead in 2018 Digital will continue reshaping the Indian Insurance Landscape.

Insurance Sector in India:

Insurance industry in India has seen a major growth in the last decade along with an introduction of a huge number of advanced products. This has led to a tough competition with a positive and healthy outcome.

Insurance sector in India plays a dynamic role in the wellbeing of its economy. It substantially increases the opportunities for savings amongst the individuals, safeguards their future and helps the insurance sector form a massive pool of funds.

With the help of these funds, the insurance sector highly contributes to the capital markets, thereby increasing large infrastructure developments in India.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In the present section an attempt has been made to examine the review of literature related to the study.

Bapat, H.B., Soni, V., Joshi, R. (2014) studied the products offering of largest public sector , Life Insurance Corporation of India and the private sector giant ICICI Prudential Life Insurance Company Limited on the aspects of applicability of SERQUAL dimensions to current product offering .

Kotgiri, S. (2013), has focused on working of insurance players in Indian scenario and comparison in terms of growth in insurance industry and trend of customers of investing amount in particular plans. Some important aspects like amount of investment habits change in attitude of customer's investment, importance given to the type of business organization are also analyzed.

Investments and Recent Developments:

The following are some of the major investments and developments in the Indian insurance sector.

- In September 2018, HDFC Ergo launched 'E@Secure' a cyber insurance policy for individuals.
- Insurance sector companies in India raised around Rs 434.3 billion (US\$ 6.7 billion) through public issues in 2017.
- In 2017, insurance sector in India saw 10 merger and acquisition (M&A) deals worth US\$ 903 million.

- India's leading bourse Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) will set up a joint venture with Ebix Inc to build a robust insurance distribution network in the country through a new distribution exchange platform.

Government Initiatives

The Government of India has taken a number of initiatives to boost the insurance industry. Some of them are as follows:

- National Health Protection Scheme will be launched under Ayushman Bharat to provide coverage of up to Rs 500,000 (US\$ 7,723) to more than 100 million vulnerable families. The scheme will be launched on September 25, 2018.
- Over 47.9 million famers were benefitted under Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in 2017-18.
- The Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI) plans to issue redesigned initial public offering (IPO) guidelines for insurance companies in India, which are to looking to divest equity through the IPO route.
- IRDAI has allowed insurers to invest up to 10 per cent in additional tier 1 (AT1) bonds that are issued by banks to augment their tier 1 capital, in order to expand the pool of eligible investors for the banks.

The Indian Insurance Sector:

The Indian Insurance Sector is basically divided into two categories – Life Insurance and Non-life Insurance. The Non-life Insurance sector is also termed as General Insurance. Both the Life Insurance and the Non-life Insurance is governed by the IRDAI (Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India).

This government organization thoroughly monitors the entire insurance sector in India and also acts like a custodian of all the insurance consumer rights. This is the reason all the insurers have to abide by the rules and regulations of the IRDAI. The Insurance sector in India consists of total 57 insurance companies. Out of which 24 companies are the life insurance providers and the remaining 33 are non-life insurers. Out which there are seven public sector companies.

Life insurance companies offer coverage to the life of the individuals, whereas the non-life insurance companies offer coverage with our day-to-day living like travel, health, our car and bikes, and home insurance. Not only this, but the non-life insurance companies provide coverage for our industrial equipment's as well. Crop insurance for our farmers, gadget insurance for mobiles, pet insurance etc. are some more insurance products being made available by the general insurance companies in India.

The life insurance companies have gained an investment prospectus in the recent times with an idea of providing insurance along with a growth of your savings. But, the general insurance companies remain reluctant to offer pure risk cover to the individuals.

Let us look at the Performance Highlights of the Indian Insurance Industry:

Life Insurance Performance:

Life Insurance Business Performance:	2015-16		2014-15	
	Public Sector	Private Sector	Public Sector	Private Sector
Premium Underwritten (Rs in Crores)	266444.21	100499.02	239667.65	88433.49
New Policies Issued (in Lakhs)	205.47	61.92	201.71	57.37
Number of Offices	4892	6179	4877	6156
Benefits Paid (Rs in Crores)	141201.05	60565.05	144125	67054
Individual Death Claims (Number of Policies)	761983	114697	755901	121927
Individual Death Claims Amount Paid (Rs in Crores)	9690.17	2946.49	9055.18	2733.49
Group Death Claims (Number of lives)	247504	297833	273794	192989
Group Death Claims Amount Paid (Rs in Crores)	2494.03	2303	2037.27	1483.55
Individual Death Claims (Figures in percent of policies)	98.33	91.48	98.19	89.4
Group Death Claims (Figures in percent of lives covered)	99.69	94.65	99.64	91.2
No. of Grievances reported during the year	64750	139951	80944	198048
Grievances resolved during the year	64750	145125	80944	193119
Grievance Resolved (in percent)	100	103.69	100	97.51

Non-Life Insurance Performance:

Non-Life Insurance Business Performance:		2015-16			2014-15			
		Public Sector	Private Sector		Public Sector	Private Sector		
Premium Underwritten (Rs in Crores)		47691	39694		42549.48	35090.09		
New Policies Issued (in Lakhs)		8414	2389		8207	2200		
Number of Offices		4892	6179		4877	6156		
Net Incurred Claims (Rs in Crores)		38104.27	21764.44		31567.75	19430.46		
No. of Grievances reported during the year		17808	41802		15860	44828		
Grievances resolved during the year		17718	42493		16105	43318		
Grievance Resolved (in percent)		99.49	101.65		101.54	96.63		
Stand Alone Health Insurance Companies	2015-16				2014-15			
	Gross Direct Premium	Net earned premium (Rs in	U/W Profit / Loss	Net incurred claim	Gross Direct Premium	Net earned premium (Rs in	U/W Profit / Loss	Net Incurred claim

Non-Life Insurance Business Performance:			2015-16			2014-15		
	(Rs in Crores)	Crores)	(Rs in Crores)	ratio	(Rs in Crores)	Crores)	(Rs in Crores)	ratio
Star Health and Allied Insurance	2007	1513	N.A.	53.81%	1469	1017	N.A.	63.96%
Apollo Munich Health Insurance	1022	774	N.A.	64.61%	803	655	N.A.	60.03%
Max Bupa Health Insurance	476	393	N.A.	59.53%	372	315	N.A.	55.16%
Religare Health Insurance	503	287	N.A.	57.25%	275	154	N.A.	61.13%
Cigna TTK Health Insurance	143	70	N.A.	78.66%	21	6	N.A.	64.33%
Specialised Insurer in Agriculture	2015-16				2014-15			
	Gross Direct Premium (Rs in Crores)	Net earned premium (Rs in Crores)	U/W Profit / Loss (Rs in Crores)	Net incurred claim ratio	Gross Direct Premium (Rs in Crores)	Net earned premium (Rs in Crores)	U/W Profit / Loss (Rs in Crores)	Net Incurred claim ratio
Agriculture Insurance Co. Ltd.	3521	1862	61.66	99.66%	2740	1598	Loss 158	108.47%
Specialised Insurer in export credit insurance	2015-16				2014-15			
	Gross Direct Premium (Rs in Crores)	Net earned premium (Rs in Crores)	U/W Profit / Loss (Rs in Crores)	Net incurred claim ratio	Gross Direct Premium (Rs in Crores)	Net earned premium (Rs in Crores)	U/W Profit / Loss (Rs in Crores)	Net Incurred claim ratio
Export Credit Guarantee Corporation of India Limited	1321	979	Loss 250	102%	1362	1019	Loss 291.91	114%

Source: Annual Report (2015-16 & 2014-15)

The Past of Insurance Sector In India

In the history of the Indian insurance sector, a decade back LIC was the only life insurance provider. Other public sector companies like the National Insurance, United India Insurance, Oriental Insurance and New India Assurance provided non-life insurance or say general insurance in India.

However, with the introduction of new private sector companies, the insurance sector in India gained a momentum in the year 2000. Currently, 24 life insurance companies and 30 non-life insurance companies have been aggressive enough to rule the insurance sector in India.

But, there are yet many more insurers who are awaiting for IRDAI approvals to start both life insurance and non-life insurance sectors in India.

The Present of Insurance Sector In India

So far as the industry goes, LIC, New India, National Insurance, United insurance and Oriental are the only government ruled entity that stands high both in the market share as well as their contribution to the Insurance sector in India. There are two specialized insurers – Agriculture Insurance Company Ltd catering to Crop Insurance and Export Credit Guarantee of India catering to Credit Insurance. Whereas, others are the private insurers (both life and general) who have done a joint venture with foreign insurance companies to start their insurance businesses in India.

Life Insurance Companies:

Private Sector Companies

- Aegon Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Aviva Life Insurance Co. India Ltd.
- Bajaj Allianz Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Bharti AXA Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Birla Sun Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Canara HSBC Oriental Bank of Commerce Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- DHFL Pramerica Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Edelweiss Tokio Life Insurance Co. Ltd
- Exide Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Future Generali India Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- HDFC Standard Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- ICICI Prudential Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- IDBI Federal Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- IndiaFirst Life Insurance Co. Ltd
- Kotak Mahindra Old Mutual Life Insurance Ltd.
- Max Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- PNB MetLife India Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Reliance Life Insurance Co. Ltd.

- Sahara India Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- SBI Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Shriram Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Star Union Dai-Ichi Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Tata AIA Life Insurance Co. Ltd.

General Insurance Companies:

Private Sector Companies

- Aditya Birla Health Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Bajaj Allianz General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Bharti AXA General Insurance Co.Ltd.
- Cholamandalam General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Future Generali India Insurance Co.Ltd.
- HDFC ERGO General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- ICICI Lombard General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- IFFCO-Tokio General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Kotak General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- L&T General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Liberty Videocon General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Magma HDI General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Raheja QBE General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Reliance General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Royal Sundaram Alliance Insurance Co. Ltd
- SBI General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Shriram General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- TATA AIG General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Universal Sompo General Insurance Co.Ltd.

Health Insurance Companies

- Apollo Munich Health Insurance Co.Ltd.
- Star Health Allied Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Max Bupa Health Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Religare Health Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Cigna TTK Health Insurance Co. Ltd.

This collaboration with the foreign markets has made the Insurance Sector in India only grow tremendously with a high current market share. India allowed private companies in insurance sector in 2000, setting a limit on FDI to 26%, which was increased to 49% in 2014. IRDAI states – Insurance Laws (Amendment) Act, 2015 provides for enhancement of the Foreign Investment Cap in an Indian Insurance Company from 26% to an Explicitly Composite Limit of 49% with the safeguard of Indian Ownership and Control.

Private insurers like HDFC, ICICI and SBI have been some tough competitors for providing life as well as non-life products to the insurance sector in India.

The Future of Insurance Sector in India:

Though LIC continues to dominate the Insurance sector in India, the introduction of the new private insurers will see a vibrant expansion and growth of both life and non-life sectors in 2017. The demands for new insurance policies with pocket-friendly premiums are sky high. Since the domestic economy cannot grow drastically, the insurance sector in India is controlled for a strong growth.

With the increase in income and exponential growth of purchasing power as well as household savings, the insurance sector in India would introduce emerging trends like product innovation, multi-distribution, better claims management and regulatory trends in the Indian market.

The government also strives hard to provide insurance to individuals in a below poverty line by introducing schemes like the

- Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana (PMSBY),
- Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY) and
- Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana (PMJJBY).

Introduction of these schemes would help the lower and lower-middle income categories to utilize the new policies with lower premiums in India.

With several regulatory changes in the insurance sector in India, the future looks pretty awesome and promising for the life insurance industry. This would further lead to a change in the way insurers take care of the business and engage proactively with its genuine buyers.

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